

Case Study

Newborn genetic screening, how far one should go?

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Abstract

Every coin has two faces; every new technology should not be used indiscriminately. DNA sequencing technology gave the rope for pinpointing mutated genes. After assessing the medical diagnosis by symptoms and signs, one can proceed for advanced molecular diagnosis such as protein, RNA and DNA sequencing methods to find gene variants for right type of therapeutic strategies. Sequencing the entire genome of all newborns is a time-consuming process and involve many ethical, financial, legal issues and instead it is a good idea if we restrict and target this useful technology to well-understood and usable gene variants only.

Keywords: Gene, Sequencing, newborn, screening, variant

Introduction

Newborn screening for genetic and metabolic disorders has helped to know the inborn errors involved in metabolism and their actual incidence and prevalence. The earlier goal of this was to know the treatable or curable disorders present in the patients instead of just documenting the data to know the prevalence and incidence of diseases [1, 2].

In humans' mothers only contribute mitochondria to off-springs [3], and therefore more genetic material is contributed by mothers. Genetic testing is useful in many areas, for e.g., testing for a genetic disorder such as Fragile X or clue about to cancer development [4]. Genetic disorders can be tested starting from karyotype to DNA sequencing. Nevertheless, in few cases, testing for genetic disorders increases the family members tension as the testing reveals the information about other members of the family along with the one tested [5].

In most cases, babies at the time of delivery appear normal and healthy but later after weeks to months. They usually do not begin showing symptoms until a few weeks or months they start showing signs and symptoms of genetic disorders [1]. Identification of such disorders and earlier treatment helps in elimination or reduction of symptoms which otherwise may cause a disability of a lifetime [6]. With the intention of protecting every child from diseases, "Genomic Revolution" was started, with a promise that whole genome sequence and genomics may play an important role in providing all children "personalized, predictive and preventive health care [7].

With the developments in DNA sequencing technology genome sequencing costs are decreased and therefore scientists are of the opinion that all newborn should be sequenced at birth to help a lifetime personal medical care. The process has the advantage that others in the family also get benefited. The medicines used to correct these disorders can also be studied

to know whether they are effective in such genetic diseases. However, sequencing data are variable and too much and the medical understanding of the same is either incomplete or misunderstood. Few data are used to enhance medical care, but other are still uncertain and hence, its widespread and untargeted use is ill-advised [8]. Therefore, care must be taken in utilizing the sequencing data depending on the needs of individual babies, families and health systems.

Human genome analysis

A very large data is arrived out of whole genome sequencing and mapping of every base pair and there are about three billion base pairs in the entire human genome [9]. The analysis of these data is carried out by the comparison of an individual's sequence to one or more reference databases and generation of a list of differences called as "gene variants". Thus, some of such gene variants are responsible for diseases, disabilities and other kinds of mental or physical disorders. Others have weak associations with specific conditions or traits [10].

There are so many complexities to interpret the sequencing data scientists are trying to solve some of these, but it is a difficult task which may never be resolved full. Sometimes, best-studied gene variants also give surprising results and remain complicated in several ways. For example, BRCA gene variants in a person are strong association with breast and ovarian cancer, but she may never get sick [11]. When disease is certain due to the presence of rare genes, the starting age of disease may be different and significant.

The expression of genes is different in different individuals. For example, Marfan syndrome may cause early life few troubling symptoms in a few, whereas many others show life-threatening heart problems by birth [12]. Family members sometimes may express the same variants differently, one with more severity and the other not much.

Newborns can't provide the consent for testing of conditions that adults hesitate to give. Hence, more caution is needed before the testing. Not only this, the phenotypic information on infants and its interpretation of results is very less available and parents will be unnecessary stress on knowing the results which sometimes be wrong predictions and which may also cause disruption of family bonding [13].

Decision on DNA sequencing for newborns should depend on the conditions which are serious and threatening the life. Priority shall also be given to those diseases which can be treated well effectively within a short time, and the results are reliable and detection easy.

There are many legal and ethical issues also involved in the newborn screening criteria. Many times, the parents or legal guardians may not agree for testing on religious grounds with acknowledgement in writing that they know the consequences of such a refusal that their newborn is at risk for undiagnosed heritable conditions.

But the above issues are individual matters and entirely different from the indiscriminate use of the whole genome sequencing in all infants as suggested by a few scientists [14]. The new technologies in health care must be used depending on the best matches on the needs of children and families who are at risk. The sequencing analysis is correct for a new born in the neonate intensive units whose disease identification is difficult and a puzzle and not be correct for rest millions of usually healthy babies, whose parents doesn't need unnecessary risk involved in the new technology. If the sequencing is used in targeted and nuanced way, it will benefit the babies, families and society for a long term.

All these various kinds of uncertainties and variabilities between thousands of gene variants make the sequencing a waste exercise in terms of affordability and use of resources if applied to all newborns and hence, limiting its usefulness to a few sequencing results is a better option. Presently only some variants help in the diagnosis, change a person's medical care, or guide important life decisions like whether to have children or not. The results of sequencing are very much useful, but dealing with a large number of questionable values to get a few results to help to a child is unnecessary.

Scientists are of the opinion that though genomics is a powerful tool, but the results it provides are still un-understood and have not been proven to advance health other than very specific clinical situations [5]. They also recommend the utilization of genomics to help in the diagnosis of sick newborns, but they draw a sharp distinction between that kind of focused clinical use and population screening. But while sequencing the genomes of some infants may be appropriate in specific cases, genome-wise sequencing of all newborns should not be carried out now.

Risks and limitations

Very small physical risks are associated with many genetic tests, especially the tests which need only a sample of blood or buccal smear (sample cells collected from the cheek inside surface). The procedures used for prenatal diagnostic testing (called amniocentesis and chorionic villus sampling) carry a small but real risk of losing the pregnancy (miscarriage) because they require a sample of amniotic fluid or tissue from around the fetus.

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Many of the risks associated with genetic testing involve the emotional, financial, or social consequences of the test results. People may feel angry, anxious, depressed, or guilty about their results. The risk of revealing the information about other family members which creates pressure also exists [15]. Above all, genetic sequencing provides only a limited information about an inherited condition. The analysis more times can't inform about the severity of a symptoms of a disorder, duration of the progress of the disorder and other details. Other major drawback is the availability of only a few treatment strategies for many genetic disorders, once they are diagnosed.

Therefore, in conclusion, we hereby propose that instead of sequencing the entire genome of all newborns, it is a good idea if we restrict and target this useful technology to well-understood and usable gene variants only.

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